

Exploiting Cross-Domain Knowledge of Large Language Models for Robust Healthcare Applications

Machine learning (ML) is widely used to address challenges in healthcare. For instance, ML is applied in the early detection of diseases such as cancer and improving treatments of neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. ML models have shown promise in the domain of drug discovery by accelerating virtual screening. While the models used can achieve high accuracy, there are various challenges that these models face, including data shift and domain shift, which can impact performance in real-world usage. Other issues, such as limited datasets and imbalanced labels, can also negatively impact performance. In this work, I aim to address this problem by exploiting a Large Language Model (LLM). This is because the extensive and diverse data used in training such models enables a cross-domain capability, as knowledge gained from one task assists in another. I experimented with multiple datasets of different sizes for both regression and classification. Generative Pretrained Network (GPT- 4o) significantly outperformed the standalone models even in conditions of a limited training set. For Example, in terms of the F1 - score, the generative models achieved a remarkable 0.90, while the artificial neural network (ANN) and XGBoost achieved 0.50 and 0.60, respectively. While all the models performed well in the regression task of virtual screening, GPT- 4o achieved the lowest Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 0.10 and 0.12 for the training set size of 25% and 35%, respectively. The result of this work has indicated the potential of LLMs to improve and address bioinformatics tasks, ultimately providing reliability in this critical field.

Keywords: Large Language Models, Machine Learning, Healthcare Applications, Disease Detection, Drug Discovery, Cross-Domain Learning, Pretrained Models

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Background Research

Machine learning has made remarkable progress in our lives. There has been an increase in domains incorporating ML to address existing challenges. This has been due to the increased computational power of computer chips and the increase in the size of data that have brought about large corpora. There are models used in many domains such as finance, autonomous systems, retail, agriculture, entertainment and defence. In autonomous vehicles, for instance, more vehicles leverage ML to increase passenger safety through predictive modelling to avoid accidents. In agriculture, algorithms are used in analysing data from satellites and drones to provide information about crop health. However, one critical field is healthcare and particularly bioinformatics. Although ML has been applied by various researchers, there are still challenges. These include domain and data shifts that negatively impact real-world usage, leading to models with high accuracies in controlled environments failing in diverse scenarios. In other cases, datasets can be limited in size, and the labels can be imbalanced or not present. Another challenge is privacy. This is one of the factors that make it difficult to access large datasets apart from the issue that medical data is not widely available compared to other types of datasets that are available online. Medical institutions do not always provide access to such data due to its sensitivity. All these limit the availability of such diverse datasets. Furthermore, there could also be a limited number of researchers in this particular domain. This could be because, on many occasions, domain knowledge and machine learning technical knowledge are required to produce high-quality research. Furthermore, the black box nature of such models also poses challenges; this can make it difficult for healthcare professionals to trust and interpret because it is often human life that is at stake. Additionally, ensuring that ML models are equitable and do not exhibit biases that are present in the training data can also pose challenges. This is important because biased models could lead to disparities in the treatment of different patients. Lastly, the availability of programming tools to process medical records in various formats is also limited. All these factors significantly hindered the advancement of this critical field.

It is of utmost importance to address most of these challenges as there are current regions across the globe facing very critical health challenges as a result of limited medical professionals and socio-economic factors. More robust mobile and portable Artificial Intelligence devices that rely on ML need to be deployed in very remote areas to increase healthcare access. This underscores the importance and the criticality of the domain.

Machine Learning models have been used for the early detection of diseases such as cancer and diabetes and neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. For example, a work by Tahmoonesi et al. [1] leverages various models, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), to effectively predict breast cancer. The authors reported having more than 90% accuracy for predicted cancer from MRI images. Walker et al. [2] also leveraged used Neural networks to predict Colorectal cancer. The authors reported that the developed system produced a median accuracy of 99.9% for normal slides and 94.8% for cancer slides when compared to diagnostics based on pathologies on H&E stain slides from clinical

samples. Additionally, Kavitha et al. [3] utilised ML models to predict Alzheimer's disease with an accuracy of 83% and reported that the developed models improve early diagnosis and reduce mortality rates. Similarly, Kopita et al. [5] also utilised a regressive ML model to predict fasting plasma glucose levels for undiagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus with a remarkable average RMSE as low as 0.838. Furthermore, a work by Liu et al. [5] leverages a deep learning model in diagnosing Alzheimer's disease with its prodromal stage (Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI)). They reported that their workflow requires less labelled training data and can analyse multiple classes in one setting. Another particular domain under bioinformatics is drug design. This is often a lengthy process due to the stringent safety standards and the critical nature of the stage involved. For example, identification is a stage that relies on virtual screening to dock millions of prospect molecules to be docked onto a target protein (associated with diseases) to inhibit its activity. This stage presents challenges such as the computational power to process a vast number of molecules, experimenting with various techniques to accurately compute the docking of large libraries of molecules relies on very costly software. There are a lot of works that have attempted to use ML to speed up the *target identification* process. For instance, a work titled “Deep-Docking” by Gentile et al. [6] leverages a QSAR model as the input to predict docking scores. The authors reported using FRED docking software and data from the ZINC15 library to calculate docking scores of more than 1.36 billion molecules on six different target proteins. They reported that the design system could detect 60% of the active molecules using a docking score of a few hundred thousand molecules. Furthermore, in my previous work titled *Accelerating Molecular Docking with Machine Learning Models* [7], we employed a model trained on a fraction of the dataset to predict the docking scores between molecules. Our system required no High-Performance Computing (HPC) environment to easily train a model to accelerate virtual screening. Another active research in Bioinformatics is predicting the structure of proteins. Understanding the structures of proteins is crucial due to their functions, which rely on their three-dimensional shape. Accurately predicting such shapes is challenging due to the complexity of the protein's folding. This folding can be in an immense variety of shapes. This prediction also requires vast computation resources. AlphaFold [8] by DeepMind has made progress in this domain. They also have a web server for researchers to predict the structures of their proteins. They reported leveraging Reinforcement Learning and Deep Learning to archive their results. The ability to predict the structure of proteins could lead to groundbreaking advancements in medicine and biotechnology and a better understanding of diseases at a molecular level.

The work aims to address one of the main challenges in bioinformatics, to improve the training process of the models used in tasks such as disease early detection and classification. The goal is to compare standalone models with Large models that have been trained on datasets beyond medical ones. This is because such datasets have the ability for cross-domain knowledge, as knowledge gained from one task assists in another. It has been to be resisting in data and domain shifts. I compared standalone alone models with Large Language Models fine-tuned on the same datasets to gain insights into the advantages the Large models can provide. The datasets are in three different domains: the first is the **Gait in Aging and Disease Dataset** for Parkinson's

detection, the **Stroke Prediction Dataset**, which relies on features such as gender and age to predict stroke and the virtual screening dataset from BadayLab to estimate the binding affinity between molecules. Additionally, the models were trained with a 25% and 35% training set size. Also, each of the datasets has specific characteristics that stand-alone models struggle with. For example, the stroke dataset contains limited data and unbalanced labels. In essence, the goal is not to fine-tune or get the best models on a specific task but to assess the capability of the models in different scenarios. After the experiments, I observed that the generative model indeed outperformed all the other models for all the cases. For example, for the hardest task of stroke detection, it achieved a remarkable f1 score of 0.88 and 0.90 for the training set size of 25% and 35%, respectively. Both ANN and XGBoost achieved an F1 score of less than 0.60 for all the cases. The only task all three models performed with high accuracy was the binding affinity prediction, where all the models achieved an MAE of less than 1.0. However, even in this task, the lowest MAE, which is 0.10, was achieved by the generative model.

Materials and Methods

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of fine-tuned generative models compared to standalone models on three different datasets: one dataset for Parkinson's detection, one for stroke detection and another for predicting the docking scores between molecules. For all the datasets, the models were trained on a training size of 25% and 35%. The aim is to ultimately understand how the models can perform in a wide range of scenarios.

Datasets

Below is the list of all the datasets used in the experiments. The datasets were chosen from different combinations of types based on regression or classification and size, from small, medium and relatively large. By experimenting with different sizes of data, for example, I can understand if there are specific cases in a specific model that would offer advantages. It is crucial to point out that the aim is to obtain models that achieve high accuracies after rigorous parameter tuning but to compare the models in different scenarios. In essence, datasets that would often require fine-tuning for the standalone models were carefully selected. Issues such as dataset class imbalance and limited data availability that standalone models struggle with were some of the factors considered in interpreting the results. Bioinformatics tasks such as for particular disease detection, metrics such as precision and recall are very important. Obtaining models that achieve high accuracies in these metrics is crucial to avoid false negatives and false positives. For the task of stroke and Parkinson's detection, there are already models available that have been optimised to carry such tasks.

- 1. Gait in Aging and Disease Dataset:** This is a Parkinson's detection that relies on the time and stride Interval of individuals categorised into three distinct classes, namely old, young and Parkinson's disease. This is a multiclass classification dataset and is categorised as a medium-sized dataset.
- 2. Stroke Detection Dataset:** This is a dataset from Kaggle that relies on features such as gender, age, and residency type to detect stroke. This is an unbalanced dataset that provides an opportunity to understand how a generative model can handle such a scenario. This is a binary classification dataset and is categorised as a small dataset.
- 3. Virtual screening Dataset:** This contains data in the form of a molecular Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILE). It is used in predicting the binding affinity between a Ligand (associated with a drug) and a target Protein (associated with a drug). The particular Protein used is Drp1_GTPase, which is usually associated with neurological diseases such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's. This dataset is a regression dataset and categorised and relatively large.

The data was chosen from different domains to gain solid insights into the potential of the LLM. I have already confirmed that none of the datasets were used in training any of the generative models

I used for the experiments. OpenAI [11] policy already states that it does not use proprietary medical data from sources such as Kaggle or PysioNet in training it. explicitly states so. Additionally, PysioNet Datasets, for example, are governed by strict ethical guidelines that restrict the usage of datasets for research purposes.

Figure 1. Flow Diagram of the project

Models

This study utilises two traditional machine learning models: Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and XGBoost. The models were trained on the aforementioned datasets. For the generative mode, I opted to use GPT-4o, which has a context length of 128k characters. The context length is the maximum amount of data length the model can process at a time. Open AI has public APIs that I used to fine-tune the model. Generative models require enormous computational power to be trained; this is both costly and time-consuming. However, the use of APIs eliminates this challenge, thereby making the experiments easier. Both the standalone models and the generative model were trained using standard training procedures, that is, without using any cross-validation.

I opted to use different training set sizes to understand how this also influences the accuracy in terms of the various metrics. Due to the size of the data, the standalone models did not require special hardware for training, and their experiments could easily be replicated on a personal computer. OpenAI api key is only what is required to try the generative model experiments. However, it is important to be cautious when fine-tuning the generative model, as the cost can quickly skyrocket. Additionally, it is also important to point out that due to the stochasticity of the generative models, the result can vary but is still negligible. The cost of this particular stage is discussed in the later section.

Evaluating Metrics

Different metrics were used in interpreting the results of the models. While most of the classification tasks rely on accuracy, I focusd on metrics that are important in real-world applications of the models. Medical datasets are very critical as it is important to avoid flagging data as either false positive or false negative. This is why metrics such as Precision, Recall and F1-score were utilised to analyse the results. Additionally, the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve was also utilised to gain insights into trade-offs between true positive rates and false positive rates. For the virtual screening dataset, Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was used to measure the average magnitude of the errors. The below list contains the definition and the importance of each of the metrics, particularly for healthcare applications.

- **Precision**

Definition: This is the fraction of the positive predictions that are correct. High precision indicates that when the model predicts a positive outcome, it is often correct.

Clinical Significance: It is important to note that false positives can lead to unnecessary treatments. In cancer screening, for example, high precision would reduce the number of patients wrongfully informed that they have cancer.

Formula: $P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$

- **Recal (Sensitivity)**

Definition: Fraction of the true positives a model identifies. High recall indicates that the model is good at identifying positive cases(a particular disease, for example)

Clinical Significance: This is important in scenarios where missing a diagnosis could lead to severe health consequences. For example, failing to detect a cancer.

Formula: $P = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$

- **F1 Score**

Definition: This computes the harmonic mean of precision and recall. High F1 indicates model performances are good for precision and recall.

Clinical Significance: This is important in cases where both cases of false positives and false negatives can carry significant risks. A high F1 score indicates the model can manage risks effectively

Formula:
$$P = 2 \frac{PR}{P+R}$$

Software and Tools

Python was the primary programming language. PyTorch was used in training the ANN and XGBoost library for training the XGBoost model. The Data Processing Tools used are Pandas and Numpy. The results were visualized using Matplotlib.

Results

After experimenting with the three models and different training set sizes. In all of the cases, the generative model consistently outperformed the remaining models. In the most difficult task of stroke detection, where not only was the dataset size limited but contained limited labels for the training set size of 25%, while ANN and XGBoost achieved an F1- score of 0.15 and 0.55, respectively, the GPT-4o achieved a score of 0.86. This indicates that the model's outputs can be reliable and indicates that it can be reliable in real-world usage. The result is similar when the training set size increases to 35%. While the F1 score increased for the generative model, it decreased for the ANN; this further indicates the difficulty of the task, which often requires very extensive parameter tuning to achieve higher scores for an ANN. This high F1 score indicates a high precision and recall for the model, metrics crucial for true positives.

Furthermore, in terms of Parkinson's detection task, while both the standalone models showed improved performance in all the metrics for different training set sizes, it is still insufficient for real-world deployment. For instance, while the ANN achieved an F1 score of 0.52, a score significantly higher than that of the stroke detection dataset for the training set size of 25%, it remains inadequate for reliability in real-world usage. XGBoost's F1 score of 0.68 demonstrates an advantage of the model compared to ANN, which often requires fine-tuning. For both of the standalone models, the results remained largely unchanged with the higher training set size of 35%, indicating the persistent challenges the models face due to the nature of the data are very persistent models. For instance, XGBoost achieved the same precision and recall of 0.67 and 0.74 for both training set sizes. Lastly, in the task of predicting binding affinity. All the models achieved a reliable MAE. ANN has the highest score for both cases of the training set sizes, 0.82 for 25% and

0.76 for 35%. XGBoost consistently outperforms ANN, highlighting its advantage in these tasks. The result of XGBoost also indicated that even though back propagation-based learning is powerful, it often comes at the cost of rigorous fine-tuning and a large amount of training data. The generative model performed exceptionally well, achieving MAE scores of 0.12 and 0.10 for the training set size of 25% and 35%, respectively, further indicating the potential of the cross-domain knowledge of the model.

Table 1: Gait in Aging and Disease Dataset

Model	25%			35%		
	F1 Score	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
Neural Network	0.52	0.58	0.63	0.51	0.58	0.62
XGBoost	0.68	0.67	0.74	0.68	0.67	0.74
GPT-4o	0.89	0.89	0.90	0.92	0.92	0.93

Table 2: Stroke Detection Dataset

Model	25%			35%		
	F1 Score	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
Neural Network	0.14	0.52	0.55	0.10	0.52	0.53
XGBoost	0.55	0.54	0.58	0.55	0.54	0.60
GPT-4o	0.86	0.85	0.88	0.90	0.90	0.90

Table 3: Virtual screening Dataset

Model	25%	30%
Neural Network	0.83	0.76
XGBoost	0.22	0.21
GPT-4o	0.12	0.10

Figure 2: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) of the standalone models on the classification datasets

Figure 3: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) of the generative model on the classification datasets

The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) is used in visualising the performance of a model for classification tasks. It plots the true positive rate (TPR) against the false positive rate (FRP); it essentially measures the distinguishing ability of the model amongst different classes. Just like the other metrics, it also has importance in medical settings. It relies on a threshold, the point at which to determine if a predicted probability is to be classified as positive or negative. ROC is characterised by a single scalar value, which is also defined as the Area Under the Curve (AUC). AUC measures the probability of ranking a random positive class higher than a randomly chosen negative class. This metric ranges from 0 to 1. A model with an AUC of 1 is considered perfect, while a model with an AUC = 0.5 is considered a random model, and a model with an AUC < 0.5 is considered the worst. Both Figures 2 and 3 can be observed to gain virtual insights into the performance of the models for the classification tasks. The ANN achieved an AUC of 0.84 for stroke detection. While this is a higher score compared to the other metrics like the F1-score, it indicates that while the model can separate the classes with good accuracy, it fails to find the right threshold, leading to a poor F1 score of 0.1. This is also similar to the Gait in Aging and Disease dataset for ANN, while the F1 score is a higher 0.51, the average AUC is lower 0.73 compared to the stroke dataset. Furthermore, XGBoost achieved a lower AUC of 0.79 compared to ANN, and while this is less favourable, it still achieved a high F1 score. ANN achieved a high AUC even though other metrics are poor, especially for stroke detection, which might have been the effect of the imbalanced class labels. However, for the Gait in Aging and Disease dataset, XGBoost achieved an average micro average AUC of 0.88, ranked higher than ANN. Finally, the generative model consistently outperformed all the model models with an AUC of 0.94 and an average micro

average AUC of 0.94 for the stroke and Gait in Aging and Disease datasets, respectively. This further demonstrates its capabilities in handling complex patterns for medical datasets.

Challenges and Limitations

The main challenge I faced while performing the experiments was the cost of fine-tuning the generative mode. Due to the requirement to format data into natural language, the size of the datasets almost doubled. For example, for the Stroke detection dataset, prompts that included the description of each of the features had to be included; this significantly increased the token size and, consequently, the cost to fine-tune the models. Additionally, the use of multiple training set sizes also doubled the cost. This challenge ultimately limited my experiments to try different parameters such as temperature, epochs and different lower-parameter models. However, the size and performance of the GPT-4o mitigated the need for extensive experimenting with different parameters, as I was able to obtain positive results even at the point of trying my initial parameters. Traditionally, such experiments that make use of sensitive medical data can raise privacy concerns. However, since the data is already open source and is not associated with any patient, the issue of privacy becomes less. Additionally, OpenAI has already stated that it does not make use of proprietary data except when explicitly stated. Furthermore, medical data is often very difficult to obtain due to privacy concerns and the cost associated with it. This was the main reason I opted to use open-source datasets. While this was sufficient for the experiments, the inability to use more robust datasets constrained the overall analysis, considering that real-world usage is important.

Future Work

As mentioned above, the cost of fine-tuning models was the main bottleneck of performing the experiments. The solution to this problem is to use local models instead of APIs. Even though running such open source models itself comes with the challenge of needing dedicated hardware that is also costly, ultimately, important experiments that use such setup can offset the cost with time of the hardware compared to relying on APIs. Additionally, while the cost of using cloud models is high, I am also interested in comparing different popular cloud models with different parameters. This can yield more insights into the strengths and weaknesses of models based on parameter size. Furthermore, I plan to experiment with more datasets, models and training set sizes. While the choice of using just two standard models and three datasets can be limited, it still provided us with valuable insights into the potential of cross-domain knowledge of generative models for healthcare and bioinformatics.

Another ambitious idea is to use an ensemble of generative models. The embedding approach of learning uses the aggregated result of multiple models as the final prediction. This approach is known to improve accuracy. This approach also increases robustness and stability since a prediction is based on multiple models; it is less likely to be influenced by noise in the data. A promising strategy could be an ensemble or a stand-alone model dedicated to a particular task with a small parameter generative model. This can increase accuracy, given the medical nature of the datasets that such experiments make use of and significantly reduce costs. The experiments in this work have indicated that even a smaller training set size could be sufficient to achieve positive results. This work relied on open-source models; however, experimenting with proprietary datasets often only obtained from clinics would have provided crucial insights into the potential of the generative models.

Conclusion

This research provides an approach to address the issues related to traditional machine learning models used in healthcare and bioinformatics in general. The experiment included comparing a vanilla neural network, XGBoost and GPT-4o on three different datasets. These datasets include Virtual screening data from BadayLab used in accelerating molecular docking. It also included the Gait in Aging and Disease Dataset and Stroke Detection Dataset, each with different properties to experiment with different scenarios. For example, the Stroke Detection dataset is limited in size and contains imbalanced labels, while the Gait in Aging dataset provided an opportunity to address having false positives or false negatives in predictions. For each of the datasets, I experimented with a training set size of 25% and 35% of the overall dataset to explore if an increase in training data can provide significant advantages for any of the models. The Virtual Screening data was utilised for the regression task, and MAE was used as the main metric to compute the accuracy of the predicted docking scores (between the ligand and the target protein) by the models. Remarkably, the generative model achieved an MAE of 0.12 and 0.10 for the training set size of 25% and 35%, respectively. This is an indication that the model can contribute to the speeding up of virtual screening, a task step for designing new drugs. Both the neural network and XGBoost also performed well in this particular task, achieving a low of less than 1.0 in all cases. Furthermore, for the Gait in the Aging and Disease Dataset, the generative model completely outperformed the other models. Specifically, it achieved an impressive precision of 0.85 and 0.90 for the training set size of 25% and 35%, respectively. High precision indicates that when the model predicts a positive result, it is often correct. Both the recall and the F1 score are also excellent. Finally, for the most difficult task of detecting stroke, the generative model also outperformed the other models. For example, with just the training set size of 25%, it achieved 0.86, 0.85 and 0.88 of F1 score, recall and precision, respectively. In essence, while the cost of pretraining the generative model was high, it still provided an insight into the potential of exploiting the cross-domain knowledge of large language models to ultimately address many problems in Bioinformatics.

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